

Impact on rice production

Since the late 1970s, drought has caused drastic cuts in rice area in Linyi (see figure). After 1982, TDCR became more popular and by 1988 was used by all farmers. Ricefields multiplied and rough rice yield increased year after year. By 1994 there was a 33% and 26% increase in per unit area yield compared with before 1982 and up to 1988, respectively. Yields of wheat following rice also increased from 1.5 to 5.4 t ha⁻¹. Therefore, profit increased by 22%.

Yield increased because the dry-raised seedling itself was healthy and mid-late rice cultivars would be planted in time to use their 20-d-longer growth period. Pests and diseases are insignificant and rotation cropping is improved.

TDCR has several advantages: (1) it is economical in water, labor, seeds, and energy; (2) it reduces costs and labor; and (3) it ensures a good harvest despite drought or waterlogging. ■

Agronomic package for hybrid rice cultivation

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Yield stagnation or even a decline has been observed in many rice-growing areas, particularly in potentially highly productive areas. To increase rice production, a few rice hybrids have been developed and released in recent years in India. To exploit the crop's full heterotic potential, it is essential to develop a package of optimum production practices for hybrid rice cultivation. We therefore attempted to study nursery management, seeding densities, seedling ratios, transplanting dates, N management, and hybrid response at several locations under the coordinated rice improvement program.

The studies revealed that the optimum seed density of 15-20 kg in a 1,000-m² nursery and planting in the second fortnight of July (1 seedling

hill⁻¹) are ideal practices for obtaining superior grain yield in hybrids. The results also indicated that different rice hybrids performed well at different locations: Hybrid ProAgro at DRR and Faizabad; ProAgro and CRH1 at the Central Rice Research Institute and Chinsurah. The local standard HKR46 performed well at Kaul. These hybrids recorded superior grain yields and showed higher N use efficiency at these locations. Grain yield differences in the tested hybrids were not significant at Aduthurai, Mandya, and Pantnagar. As

the tests were made in the wet season, the hybrids may not have exhibited their full yield potential at Cuttack and Maruteru because of rain. The response to N was limited up to 100 kg N ha⁻¹ at Cuttack, Chinsurah, and Pantnagar, and up to 150 kg N ha⁻¹ at Aduthurai, Hyderabad, Mandya, and Faizabad. Hybrids failed to respond beyond 150 kg N ha⁻¹ at most test locations. Applying the recommended N in three splits (50% basal + 25% tillering + 25% booting) was the best management practice for hybrids in Vertisols at DRR. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement — weeds

Chemical weed control in rice nurseries of the hill zone of Karnataka

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Weeds pose a threat to rice cultivation from the nursery stage in the hill zone of Karnataka (south India), which has 182,000 ha under rainfed rice (the sole food and field crop of the zone). This area is located between 12-14° N and

74-76° E. Average annual rainfall is 2,460 mm, of which 83% occurs between June and September (with the remaining 17% from October to December). Rice nurseries are sown from the first week of June to the second week of July depending upon the toposequence and rainfall pattern for the wet season and during the second week of December to the second week of January for the summer (dry) season.

Rice nurseries are infested by grass sedges and broadleaf weeds that

Table 1. Effect of herbicides on germination of rice and dry weight of rice seedlings in the hill zone of Karnataka, India.

Treatment	Germination (%) recorded at 10 DAS ^a				Mean of 2 yr	Dry weight (av) of 10 seedlings at 25 DAS (g)				Mean of 2 yr
	Kharif (1993-94)	Summer (1994-95)	Kharif (1993-94)	Summer (1994-95)		Kharif (1993-94)	Summer (1994-95)	Kharif (1993-94)	Summer (1994-95)	
1. Control, unweeded check	92	94	94	95	94	1.06	1.13	1.12	1.27	1.19
2. Butachlor preemergence 50 EC (1.25 L ha ⁻¹)	92	94	88	92	91	2.39	2.43	2.43	2.67	2.55
3. Benthocarb-30 EC (1.25 kg ai ha ⁻¹) preemergence	74	76	68	72	72	1.84	1.94	1.96	2.01	1.98
4. Pendimethaline 30 EC (preemergence) (1.0 kg ai ha ⁻¹)	72	73	68	64	69	1.92	1.82	2.01	1.98	1.99
5. Butachlor (5%) granules (25 kg ha ⁻¹)	73	74	77	79	75	2.12	1.93	2.20	2.08	2.14
6. Anilophos 30 EC @300 mL ha ⁻¹ (3 DAS) Postemergence	89	93	90	88	90	2.26	2.33	2.32	2.46	2.39
7. Hand weeding at 10 and 20 DAS LSD (P = 0.05)	92	93	93	94	93	1.94	2.03	2.10	2.19	2.14
						0.03	0.08	0.12	0.27	0.16

^aDAS = days after sowing.